

ADJECTIVAL CLAUSES IN ENGLISH AND ALBANIAN

Syntax

Keywords: adjectival clauses, syntax, semantic, functional adjectives, identity adjectives, adjective position, determiner functional category, nominal modifiers, syntactic edges, adjective ordering.

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Abstract

This paper is to point out similarities and differences of English and Albanian language, trying to compare of both languages. Many languages do not distinguish between adjectives and names etc, i.e. the Albanian language differs in terms of gender and plural adjectives, while English has not such a feature. Therefore formal distinctions between parts of speech should be done within the framework of a given language and should not be applied in other languages. In this paper we have analyzed adjective structures in Albanian and English.

Introduction

Grammar is traditionally divided into two different but inter-related areas of study: morphology and syntax. In the paper will be analyzed some of the similarities and differences in the adjectival clauses in English and Albanian, as well as problems related to them. Similarities, but more specifically the differences, should be taken into consideration especially during the process of translation from one language to another.

In this paper we will try to address some similarities and differences in English and Albanian syntax, but of course each of them has its own special features. The rules of a language, also called grammar, are learned as one acquires a language. These rules include phonology, the sound system, morphology, the structure of words, syntax, the combination of words into sentences, semantics, the ways in which sounds and meanings are related, and the lexicon, or mental dictionary of words. When you know a language, you know words in that language, i.e. sound units or signs that are related to specific meanings. However, the sounds or signs and meanings of words are arbitrary. For the most part, there is no relationship between the way a word is pronounced (or signed) and its meaning.

In this paper we will try to explain classification for adjectives appears to be the syntactic one, distinguishing between NP-adjectives and DP-adjectives. Within nominal phrases, this contrast correlates with the semantic difference between kind-level modifiers (NP-adjectives) and object-level modifiers (DP-adjectives). Kind-level modifiers differ as to “how objective” the classification they propose is. Post nominal NP adjectives are descriptive, stylistically neutral, while prenominal NP-adjectives add a pragmatic stance (i.e., pragmaticize) on the classification.

On the theoretical side, there is evidence for a class of DP-adjectives inside the nominal phrase, described as object-level modifiers which combine with the sister DP by Functional

Application. They are predicates on the DP, exhibiting the same semantic behaviour as small clause predicates.

In our analysis, the difference between the same adjective used pre nominally and post nominally lies in the fact that in the prenominal use the adjective incorporates a pragmatic quantificational feature, with the consequence that it merges as the specifier of a periphery projection combining with its sister by Functional Application, not by Predicate Modification. This is true of both NP- and DP-adjectives. DP-internal adjectives interpreted by Functional Application are not restrictive. The adjunction configuration corresponds to direct modification and to an operation of Predicate Modification, whose output is a restrictive (intersective or subsective) interpretation. The difference between prenominal and post nominal adjectives has thus been accounted for.

The main criterion of classification for adjectives appears to be the syntactic one, distinguishing between NP-adjectives and DP-adjectives. Within nominal phrases, this contrast correlates with the semantic difference between kind-level modifiers (NP-adjectives) and object-level modifiers (DP-adjectives). Kind-level modifiers differ as to “how objective” the classification they propose is. Post nominal NP adjectives are descriptive, stylistically neutral, while prenominal NP-adjectives add a pragmatic stance (i.e., pragmaticize) on the classification.

On the theoretical side, there is evidence for a class of DP-adjectives inside the nominal phrase, described as object-level modifiers which combine with the sister DP by Functional Application. They are predicates on the DP, exhibiting the same semantic behaviour as small clause predicates. Against the more traditional view, our results on the relative order of adjectives in Albanian coincide with those of other researchers, who have shown that adjectival relative order depends on the semantic type of the adjective: in post nominal position, relative adjectives precede qualifying adjectives, and, prenominally, object-level modifiers precede kind-level ones.

The fact that the interpretation of an adjective is derived from the range of its denotations and especially from the syntactic configuration where it occurs (which determines the choice among these denotations) is clearly a syntax-semantics interface issue.

In these Conclusions, we have not only made efforts to briefly present the achievements and innovations of our research, but have also raised the problems yet to be solved. We are quite aware that all issues discussed in this wide topic, have not been fully exhausted. We hope that in the future we might come back again to research the questions that remain open, because there are more issues to be resolved than those we have already treated. The adjective is a large lexical class, with an opened inventory. It raises a number of issues, problems of the morphological, syntactic and semantic character, which require the joint efforts of independent researchers with Institutes and Departments of the Albanian language.

Consider English first. Under this view, the illusion of two distinct structural positions with the exact same set of interpretations is due to the possibility of raising the N plus any direct modification APs above an AP in a reduced RC. The case of Albanian is similar, though more complex in the movement operations that it involves. Here too the apparent existence of two direct modification positions (one preceding and one immediately following the N), with exactly the same sets of interpretations, is an illusion created by the optional raising of the N across one (or more) direct modification adjective(s); a movement followed by the obligatory raising of the N plus any direct modification adjective above an AP in are reduced RC.

The obligatory raising of the N (plus any direct modification APs) above APs in reduced relative clauses is related to the fact that differently from English the N (plus any AP) obligatorily raises above ordinary reduced RCs (participial reduced relative clauses are obligatorily post-nominal in Albanian). Syntactically, adjectives in reduced RCs are: I) necessarily predicative (though the same lexical entry may also have direct modification, non-predicative uses); II) further away from the noun than direct modification adjectives; III) maximal projections; IV) an open class; V) non-rigidly ordered.

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